

Target Detection in a Highway Scenario with Extended V2V Channel Model

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Abstract—Integrated Communication and Sensing (ICAS) represents an exciting new research field that combines communication and radar sensing functionalities under a single platform. This convergence leverages the similarities in signal processing, spectrum utilization, and system design between the two functionalities. The main difference between sensing and communication is their ability to use different segments of the propagation channel because of their distinct system requirements. In Vehicular Ad-hoc Networks (VANETs), existing channel models are designed purely for V2V (Vehicle to Vehicle) or V2X (Vehicle to Anything) communications. With the sole purpose of communication, such channel models lack the capability of radar sensing. ICAS demands simultaneous communication and target sensing. Therefore, in this paper, we extended a communication-based V2V channel model to integrate target detection, thus realizing an ICAS system. We considered a two-way highway scenario in the presence of Diffuse (DI) scattering components. DI components can result in high-power reflections for small distances. Therefore, the integration of the DI components is vital for the development of accurate target detection algorithms. In our simulations, we showed that the extended ICAS channel model can detect Dynamic Targets (DT) alongside its communication functionality. In addition, we also demonstrate the impact of a strong Direct Link (DL) between the Transmitter (Tx) and Receiver (Rx) on target detection.

Index Terms—Spatial channel models, stochastic channel models, deterministic channel models, ray-tracing, ICAS.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless communications and radar sensing are the two important pillars of modern autonomous vehicles. Both fields have been advancing in their particular domains with little or no overlap. However, in recent years, research has been conducted to unify the capabilities of both technologies. This direction of research is motivated by the fact that both systems have common functionalities such as signal processing, hardware equipment, propagation medium, and system architecture [1]. Due to the similarities between the two, Integrated Communication and Sensing (ICAS) presents a viable solution for services such as Autonomous Driving (AD), real-time eHealth monitoring, etc. ICAS will become an important technology to support many industrial applications in the near future [2].

The standard channel models are designed to present a unified framework for different technologies. Different channel models are designed to meet different performance requirements such as throughput, latency, and reliability. These include COST action projects, 3GPP Spatial Channel Model (SCM) [3], WINNER channel models [4], IEEE 802.11n [5] & IEEE 802.16ac [6], [7]. Various types of stochastic

(Geometry-based Stochastic Channel Model (GBSCM), Non-Geometry-based Stochastic Channel Model (NGBSCM)) as well as deterministic (Ray Tracing (RT)-based) models have been presented for Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V) communications [8]. However, ICAS is still in its infancy. There is no well-matured ICAS channel model found in the literature that can support communication and sensing simultaneously for the vehicular/ highway environment.

The statistical nature of the communication channel is different from that of the radar sensing channel. In communication systems, multiple paths can add to the overall received power along with spatial information. However, not all paths are relevant or even desired in the case of radar sensing [9]. For radar sensing mainly the Line-of-Sight (LoS) link (Transmitter (Tx) → Dynamic Target (DT) → Receiver (Rx)) is important, because all other paths are typically treated as unwanted clutter [10].

The channel model presented in [11] – originally designed for V2V communications – does not consider radar sensing. Therefore, we extended this channel model for radar sensing by incorporating the vehicle’s Radar Cross Section (RCS) in the original model. Our extended channel model is capable of performing communication and radar sensing simultaneously, thus realizing an ICAS channel model. To model the extended ICAS channel, we considered three links: 1) Direct Link (DL) (Tx → Rx), 2) DT Indirect Link (IDL) (Tx → DT → Rx), and 3) Diffuse (DI) IDL (Tx → DI → Rx).

The remainder of this document is structured as follows: Sec. II describes the geometry of the highway, scatterer distribution, and simulation tools. Next, Sec. III describes the extended ICAS channel model. Sec. IV shows the simulation results. Finally, Sec. V concludes the paper.

Notations: $(\cdot)^T$ represents the transpose operation.

II. HIGHWAY GEOMETRY AND SCATTERERS DISTRIBUTION

In this section, we describe the highway geometry, distribution of DI scatterers, and vehicle routes. Moreover, this section will also provide information about tools used for traffic generation and signal processing.

A. Two-way Highway Scenario Topology

For the highway, we consider a 6-lane (3-lanes per direction) highway setup for our simulations. It has a length $l_{highway}=1$ km and a width $w_{highway}=27$ m. The width of each

Fig. 1: Geometry of the highway model

lane is $w_{lane}=4.5$ m. Fig. 1 shows the lane numbers and their respective positions along with the direction of motion of the vehicles. On both sides of the road, the DI components representing vegetation, scatterers, and points of reflection beyond the road, are considered to model their impact on the overall channel performance. The width of the DI region is $w_{diff}=5$ m. The distance from the center of the road to the first DI component is $d_{diff}=15$ m. Further, we consider a boundary region of $d_{gap}=2$ m between the start of the DI region and the outermost lanes.

B. Distribution of Scatterers

In our framework, we use a fixed number of four DT that contribute towards the channel response. These DT represent moving vehicles and are placed in different lanes according to the geometry of the highway. To model the DI region, a similar approach used in [11] is adopted. The density of the DI scatterers within a given length of one meter is given by χ_{diff} . The x-coordinates of the DI scatterers are modeled by a uniform distribution i.e., $x_{diff} \sim \mathcal{U}[x_{min}, x_{max}]$. Their y-coordinates are also drawn from the uniform distribution i.e., $y_{diff} \sim \mathcal{U}[y_{1,diff} - w_{diff}/2, y_{1,diff} + w_{diff}/2]$ or $y_{diff} \sim \mathcal{U}[y_{2,diff} - w_{diff}/2, y_{2,diff} + w_{diff}/2]$, where $[y_{1,diff}]$ and $[y_{2,diff}]$ represent the center of the DI region on both sides of the highway. In our simulations, $[y_{1,diff}] = -17.5$ m and $[y_{2,diff}] = 17.5$ m.

C. Vehicles and Routes

In our paper, we considered two setups:

- Setup A: Tx and Rx are located in the middle lanes (V-1, RV-1) as shown in Fig. 1, moving in opposite directions,
- Setup B: Tx is located in the middle lane (V-1) and Rx in the innermost lane (V-2), moving in the same direction (along the +ve x-axis).

D. Simulation Tools

For our simulation, we use two mathematical tools. For the generation of traffic on the road, we use Simulation of

Urban MObility (SUMO) [12], which is an open-source tool used for simulating and analyzing traffic. We developed the highway geometry as shown in Fig. 1 in SUMO. Vehicles are assigned variable velocities and starting positions to represent a realistic scenario. The variation in the vehicles' velocities is recorded to be around ± 2 m/s. The respective positions and velocities of Tx, Rx, and DT are imported into MATLAB for signal processing. There, different channel parameters and responses for DL and IDL are calculated. Moreover, received power, excess delay, Doppler shift, trajectory information, and detection capabilities are evaluated with MATLAB.

III. ICAS EXTENDED CHANNEL MODEL

In our study, we have considered a Single Input Single Output (SISO) antenna configuration with unity gain. We have adopted the model inspired by [11]. However, the model does not consider vehicles' detection on the road. We have extended the model by dividing the link Tx \rightarrow DT \rightarrow Rx into two parts. The first half (Tx \rightarrow DT) is calculated as given in [11]. In the second half i.e., DT \rightarrow Rx, in order to detect vehicles, we have extended the model to integrate the RCS of DT. The Channel Impulse Response (CIR) can be represented as:

$$h(t) = \sum_s \alpha_s e^{j2\pi f_{D,s} t} \delta(t - \tau_s), \quad (1)$$

where τ_s and $f_{D,s}$ represent the excess delay and Doppler shift of the respective multipath s . The amplitude of the multipath s is represented by α_s . We have considered three major contributors¹ to the overall channel response in our simulations.

A. LoS Component

The LoS component defines the link between Tx and Rx when no vehicles or obstacles are blocking the DL path. The LoS channel response is given by:

$$h_l(t) = \alpha_l e^{j2\pi f_{D,l} t} \delta(t - \tau_l), \quad (2)$$

¹In our simulations, we have not considered the contributions from Static Target (ST) (road signs, signboards, etc.).

where $f_{D,l}$ and τ_l represent the Doppler shift and delay for the LoS component. The amplitude α_l is given by [11]:

$$\alpha_l = P_{0,l}^{1/2} \left(\frac{d_{ref}}{d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}} \right)^{n_l/2}, \quad (3)$$

where $P_{0,l}$ is the reference power for the LoS component at $d_{ref}=1$ m, n_l is the path-loss exponent for LoS, and $d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}$ is the LoS distance. The delay and Doppler shift for the LoS component is calculated as:

$$\tau_l = \frac{d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}}{c}, \quad (4)$$

$$f_{D,l} = \left(\frac{(\mathbf{v}_{Tx} - \mathbf{v}_{Rx})^T \cdot (\mathbf{p}_{Tx} - \mathbf{p}_{Rx})}{d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}} \right) \cdot \frac{2f_c}{c} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{v}_{Tx} , \mathbf{v}_{Rx} , f_c , and c represent Tx velocity, Rx velocity, carrier frequency, and speed of light, respectively. \mathbf{p}_{Tx} and \mathbf{p}_{Rx} are the position vectors of Tx and Rx, respectively.

B. DT Component

DT components refer to the IDL, which result from other moving vehicles on the highway, i.e. Tx \rightarrow k \rightarrow Rx (where k denotes the k^{th} DT). The DT channel response can be mathematically expressed as:

$$h_k(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k e^{j2\pi f_{D,k}t} \delta(t - \tau_k), \quad (6)$$

where $f_{D,k}$ and τ_k represent the Doppler shift and delay for the DT component. K is the total number of DT components in our scenario. The amplitude α_k is given by:

$$\alpha_k = P_{0,k}^{1/2} \left(\frac{d_{ref}}{d_{Tx \rightarrow k}} \right)^{n_k/2} \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{RCS,k}}{4\pi(d_{k \rightarrow Rx})^{n_k}}}, \quad (7)$$

where $P_{0,k}$ is the reference power for the DT component, n_k is the path-loss exponent. $d_{Tx \rightarrow k}$ and $d_{k \rightarrow Rx}$ represent the distance from Tx to k^{th} DT and k^{th} DT to Rx, respectively. $\sigma_{RCS,k}$ denotes the RCS of the k^{th} DT. The delay and Doppler shift for k^{th} DT is given as:

$$\tau_k = \frac{(d_{Tx \rightarrow k} + d_{k \rightarrow Rx})}{c}, \quad (8)$$

$$f_{D,k} = \left(\frac{\mathbf{v}_{Tx}^T \cdot (\mathbf{p}_k - \mathbf{p}_{Tx})}{d_{Tx \rightarrow k}} - \frac{\mathbf{v}_{Rx}^T \cdot (\mathbf{p}_{Rx} - \mathbf{p}_k)}{d_{k \rightarrow Rx}} \right) \cdot \frac{f_c}{c}, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{p}_k is the position vector of k^{th} DT.

C. DI Component

The DI components represent the point scatterers or vegetation located along the sides of the highway. The DI channel response can be mathematically expressed as:

$$h_{diff}(t) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \alpha_q e^{j2\pi f_{D,q}t} \delta(t - \tau_q), \quad (10)$$

where $f_{D,q}$ and τ_q represent the Doppler shift and delay for the q^{th} DI component. Q is the total number of DI scatterers in our scenario. The amplitude of DI scatterer is modeled according to the classical GBSCM approach and is represented as [11]:

$$\alpha_q = P_{0,q}^{1/2} c_q \left(\frac{d_{ref}}{d_{Tx \rightarrow q} \times d_{q \rightarrow Rx}} \right)^{n_q/2}, \quad (11)$$

where $P_{0,q}$ and n_q represent reference power and path-loss exponent for the DI component. $d_{Tx \rightarrow q}$ and $d_{q \rightarrow Rx}$ represent the distance from Tx to the q^{th} DI scatterer and from the q^{th} DI scatterer to Rx, respectively. c_q denotes zero-mean complex Gaussian variable. The delay and Doppler shift for DI scatterers can be calculated similarly to the DT components given in (8) and (9).

D. Overall Channel Response

The overall channel response is derived by adding the contributions from the individual channel responses (i.e., LoS component, DT components, and DI components), and is given as:

$$h(t) = h_l(t) + h_k(t) + h_{diff}(t). \quad (12)$$

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we present the simulation results for the aforementioned two scenarios at a carrier frequency of $f_c = 5.2$ GHz. We have considered an omnidirectional radiation pattern for the transmit and receive antennas. The vehicles' velocity in different lanes and the rest of the parameters are given in Table I.

TABLE I: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
Frequency (f_c)	5.2 GHz
Bandwidth (B)	50 MHz
Transmit Power	23 dBm
DT speed in different lanes (V-0,V-1,V-2,RV-0,RV-1,RV-2)	(32,30,27,27,30,32) m/s
Simulation Time (t_{sim})	15.99 s
Sample Time	0.01 s
Radar Cross Section (σ_{RCS})	10 dBsm
Reference Power ($P_{0,i}$) where $i \in (l, k, q)$	(-5, -10, 104) dB
PL Exponents (n_i where $i \in (l, k, q)$)	(1.8, 2.0, 5.4)
Number of DT components	4
DI Scatterers Density χ_{diff}	1 m ⁻²

In our simulations, we first determine the amplitude of the channel for the DI components with only Tx and Rx on the road according to (11). The ray/wave travels from Tx \rightarrow q \rightarrow Rx. At the Rx, the contributions from the DI scatterers are added as shown in Fig. 1². Similarly, to record the channel response for the DT, a wave traveling from Tx \rightarrow k \rightarrow Rx is calculated according to (6). At the Rx, the channel magnitudes from all DT are added to obtain a joint DT channel response. The overall channel magnitude is then calculated by summing the contributions from LoS, DT, and DI components as given in (12).

A. Setup A Simulation Results

Fig. 2a represents the individual channel magnitudes for the DL, DT, and DI components in Setup A. As expected, the DL component has the maximum amplitude. The Tx and Rx are located at the maximum distance ($d_{max}=465$ m) at the start of the simulation. The distance between Tx and Rx

²The Fig. 1 shows the DI (IDL) for only two diffuse scatterers. However, the process takes place for all the DI scatterers.

(a) DL, DT, and DI components channel magnitudes.

(b) Overall channel magnitude.

Fig. 2: Channel magnitude for Setup A.

Fig. 3: Vehicles' trajectory for Setup A over time.

$d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}$ starts to decrease as the vehicles move toward one another. In the middle of the highway, i.e. for $6s \leq t_{sim} \leq 10s$, the distance $d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}$ is at its minimum ($d_{min}=18m$), resulting in the highest channel magnitude values. After the d_{min} point, the Tx and Rx cross each other, and $d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}$ starts increasing again, which results in declining values until

(a) Snapshot at $t_{sim}=6s$.

(b) Snapshot at $t_{sim}=10s$.

Fig. 4: Distance-Velocity map for Setup A.

the end of the simulation. A similar pattern can be seen in the channel magnitudes of both DT and DI components. However, in the joint DT channel magnitudes, the peaks that appeared at different time instants represent the positions of the DT when their individual distance (i.e., $Tx \rightarrow k \rightarrow Rx$) is at its minimum. The overall channel magnitude (i.e., $h_l + h_k + h_{diff}$) is shown in Fig. 2b. The highest contribution comes from the DL component. Therefore, it follows a similar pattern. It is at its maximum at the center and lowest toward the start and end of the simulation.

The trajectory taken by the Tx (DL) and DT (lane V-0, V-2, RV-0, RV-2) is presented in Fig. 3. As shown in Fig. 1, at the start of the simulation, the Tx and DT are located at d_{max} . As the vehicles move in opposite directions, the distance decreases until the d_{min} point is reached. After the d_{min} point, vehicles cross one another and the distance starts increasing till the end of the simulation. We considered different starting positions and velocities for vehicles in different lanes as shown in Table I. As a result, the vehicles catch up with one another, and we see an overlap in the trajectory. However, the DL always results in the smallest link distance d_{link} throughout the simulation.

Fig. 4 shows the target detection performed at different

time instants. The snapshots indicate the presence of all components, i.e. DL, DT, and DI. The red and black ellipses indicate the presence of the Tx from the DL, and the DT from the IDL, respectively. The rest indicates the DI components, which are treated as clutter in the scenario. The snapshot at $t_{sim}=6$ s shows the presence of four distinct DT, one Tx, and several DI components. The DL results in the highest received power component at the Rx. The power of DI components is much lower as compared to other components. However, they are detected throughout the simulation. Vehicles in Setup A are moving in opposite directions on different sides of the road. They cross each other at $t_{sim}=8$ s. This is indicated by the change in the relative velocity of the Tx and DT. The DT in different lanes move with variable velocities. The distance of vehicles in lanes RV-0 and RV-2 from Rx becomes too small to identify them as unique targets as shown in Fig. 4b. Therefore, in the snapshot at $t_{sim}=10$ s, they appear as a single target. The detection of DI components depends on the $d_{Tx \rightarrow q \rightarrow Rx}$ and the power. For Setup A, although DI components result in low power, their inclusion in modeling ICAS channel models is of paramount significance in developing powerful detection algorithms.

B. Setup B Simulation Results

The channel magnitude for Setup B is given in Fig. 5b. The velocity of the Rx is slightly higher than the Tx's velocity. Therefore, for the DL link, the channel magnitude decreases with an increasing distance between the Tx and Rx. For the DT in lane V-0, the channel response exhibits a similar behavior as the Tx. This stems from the fact that the direction of motion for the DT in lane V-0 is similar to that of Tx. For the DT in lanes RV-0, RV-1, and RV-2, the highest channel magnitude values are recorded during $6 \text{ s} \leq t_{sim} \leq 10 \text{ s}$. At the start and end of the simulation, lower values for the channel magnitudes were observed. The joint channel magnitude for the DT depicts a similar pattern. As the starting positions of the DT are different from one another, the peak points are reached at different time instants. This results in fluctuations of the channel magnitude values during $5 \text{ s} \leq t_{sim} \leq 11 \text{ s}$. In Setup B, the distance between the Tx and the Rx is comparably small, which results in a small IDL distance and high channel magnitudes of the DI scatterers.

The trajectory taken by the vehicles in Setup B is given in Fig. 6. The direction of motion for the Tx and the DT in lane V-0 is the same as for the Rx. However, the velocities and starting positions are different. The distance between the Rx and the Tx as well as the Rx and the DT in lane V-0 via IDL remain almost constant during the simulation. The DT in lanes RV-0, RV-1, and RV-2 move in the opposite direction of the Rx. As Tx and Rx are located closely to one another, the d_{link} is much larger as compared to setup A. The d_{link} attains smaller values during the interval $7 \text{ s} \leq t_{sim} \leq 9 \text{ s}$. After 9 s, vehicles cross one another, and d_{link} starts increasing till the end of the simulation.

The snapshots for Setup B also indicate the presence of DL, DT, and DI components. The Tx is located in close proximity

(a) DL, DI, and DT channel magnitudes.

(b) Overall channel magnitude.

Fig. 5: Channel magnitude for Setup B.

Fig. 6: Vehicles' trajectory for setup B over time.

to the Rx. The DL always results in a much higher power as compared to other components in the scenario. Therefore, the Tx can be detected throughout the simulation. The DI components – depending on their respective location in the scenario – may result in a higher power component as compared to distantly located DT. The DT in lanes RV-0, RV-1, and RV-2

(a) Snapshot at $t_{sim}=6$ s.

(b) Snapshot at $t_{sim}=10$ s.

Fig. 7: Distance-Velocity map for Setup B.

are very far from the Rx. They result in low-power reflections when the distance between the Rx and the DT is too large. The snapshot at 6 s indicates that the DT are moving towards the Rx with low power reflections. However, there are DI components with equal or higher power. As a result, the detection of the DT becomes more challenging. The DT components cross the Rx at $t_{sim}=8$ s as shown in Fig. 6. This is indicated by the change in the relative velocity in Fig. 7b. Fig. 7 also shows that the DI components result in a higher power (depending upon the distance $d_{Tx \rightarrow q \rightarrow Rx}$) as compared to the DT, which can result in false detections. Therefore, it is highly crucial to incorporate the DI components in the modeling of ICAS scenarios.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we extended a V2V channel model to integrate radar sensing capabilities. We have shown that the Dynamic Target (DT) component can be masked by Diffuse (DI) components when the distance of DI components is much smaller than DT. Therefore, it is critical to consider DI components in ICAS models where accurate detection and communication are desired. As shown in our results, failing to consider DI components can give rise to ghost targets. In our results, we

have shown that the extended model can also perform the functionality of radar sensing apart from communication. We have also shown that weaker reflections from the DT can be buried by the strong Direct Link (DL) making target detection an arduous job. Thus, if we accurately model DI components and possess prior knowledge about their positions, we can efficiently eliminate clutter echoes through effective signal processing techniques, improving target detection accuracy. In the future, this work can be extended by integrating Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) setup with different antenna polarization to explore its impact on target detection and channel performance.

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